

Legal Policy Framework for the Development of Tourist Villages Based on Green Tourism in Gianyar, Bali

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Abstract: In developing green tourism, some principles and policies must exist and be pursued continuously. The direction of tourism development with the concept of green tourism must be holistically planned by considering various aspects. Such development aims to minimize the negative impacts of developing tourism in an area. The objectives of this research are to identify, analyze, and find a legal policy framework for the development of tourist villages based on green tourism in Gianyar, Bali, and the application of green tourism in the development of tourist villages. This research was prepared in a normative-empirical form using a statutory regulation approach and a conceptual and observational approach to tourist villages in Gianyar Regency. The legal material sources used in this research were primary and secondary legal material sources. This research shows that the legal policy for developing green tourism is outlined in statutory regulations and implemented based on regional government policy. The development of tourist villages in Gianyar is carried out continuously by utilizing natural, cultural, and artistic potential.

Keywords: Green Tourism, Legal Policy, Tourist Village.

1. Introduction

Tourism is an economic sector with great potential to drive the local economy, especially in rural areas [1]. Gianyar is one of the districts in Bali, Indonesia, and is a popular tourist destination. Geographically, Gianyar Regency is not an island district but consists of a unified land area. Gianyar Regency consists of 7 sub-districts: Sukawati District, Blahbatuh District, Gianyar District, Tampaksiring District, Ubud District, Tegallalang District and Payangan District. In terms of area, Payangan District is the largest sub-district in Gianyar Regency with an area of 75.88 km² or 20.62% of the total district area. Followed by Tegallalang District with an area of 60.80 km² and Sukawati District with an area of 55.02 km². Meanwhile, the smallest sub-district is Blahbatuh Sub-district, which has an area of 39.70 km² (10.79%) [2].

Tourism plays an important role in developing the nation's economy, as seen from the increasingly better and advanced economic prosperity. Increasing prosperity impacts human needs and lifestyles, making tourism a lifestyle or a basic part of needs [3]. In principle, tourism refers to: 1) Community-

based tourism: Community-based tourism has the object of the people or society as a whole which is the goal of tourism development; 2) Tourism with a cultural perspective: tourism with a cultural perspective is relying on society as its basic strength; 3) Sustainable tourism: Nature and culture are tourism capital that must be conserved (maintained, utilized and developed) [4]. Tourism activities must continue to benefit and must be maintained so that the benefits can be benefited for future generations (sustainable development).

The development of tourism concepts is directed at green tourism. In the United Kingdom, the term green tourism is closely related and is a concept that is integrated with rural tourism. This also aligns with the concept of green tourism in Japan. The concept of green tourism in developed countries such as Japan is very similar to the concept of rural tourism, where activities are in nature and provide opportunities for tourists to experience and be involved in local culture and rural lifestyle [5]. Green tourism is a form of ecotourism that focuses on sustainable tourism, meaning that it does not cause damage to the tourist sites and cultural heritage sites being visited (environmentally friendly). Some activities include hiking (walking and climbing), trekking, birding or birdwatching (bird watching), snorkeling, and diving. UNWTO states, "Green Tourism is environmentally sustainable travel to destinations where the flora, fauna, and cultural heritage are the primary attractions and where environmental impacts are minimized". It was also stated that "Green tourism refers to tourism activities that can be maintained or sustained, indefinitely in their social, economic, cultural and environmental contexts: sustainable tourism..." [6].

The implementation of the green tourism concept can be seen in the development of the tourist village's policy in Gianyar Regency, Bali. A tourist village is a rural area that generally offers an atmosphere that reflects the authenticity of the village in terms of socio-economic, socio-cultural, customs, daily life, has typical village building architecture and spatial structures, or unique economics and businesses that are interesting and have potential to develop various components of tourism [7]. The tourist village program gives the village government and

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Table 1
Number of tourist villages that have been determined through mayoral regent decrees throughout Bali [9]

Regencies	Districts	Tourist Villages	Pioneering Category	Developing Category	Advanced Category	Independent Pioneering Category
Buleleng	9	75	55	12	7	1
Tabanan	10	25	0	25	0	0
Badung	3	17	9	7	1	0
Gianyar	7	32	13	10	8	1
Klungkung	4	19	4	15	0	0
Bangli	4	31	6	19	5	1
Karangasem	9	26	9	11	6	0
Kota	3	6	0	6	0	0
Denpasar						
Jembrana	4	7	5	2	0	0

the community great authority to manage the program from planning to implementation and supervision [8].

In developing green tourism, some principles must exist and be pursued continuously. Gianyar Regency has 32 tourist villages in the following categories: pioneering, developing, advanced, and independent. Tourist destinations that are used as tourist attractions must be natural places and have a focus on environmental conservation. The direction of tourism development with the concept of green tourism must be holistically planned by considering various aspects. Such development aims to minimize the negative impacts of developing tourism in an area. Developing tourism facilities in a tourist area with the concept of green tourism by building high environmental awareness is carried out by local communities as hosts and visiting tourists (guests). Environmental awareness will ensure the future preservation and sustainability of the environment [6]. Legal policies are needed to develop tourist villages in Gianyar. Based on the explanation above, it is interesting to discuss further the development of tourist villages entitled "Legal Policy Framework for the Development of Tourist Villages Based on Green Tourism in Gianyar, Bali."

2. Research Methods

This research is structured in normative form. The normative approach is carried out using a statutory regulation and a conceptual approach so that this research leads to a concrete activity to reveal matters related to the legal policy for green tourism-based tourism village development. Legal material sources used in this research are primary and secondary legal materials. Sources of primary legal materials are obtained directly and have juridically binding legal force, and sources of secondary legal materials are from several literatures, scientific works, and research results. The method for collecting legal source materials in this research is a documentary study. Documentary study can be explained as a method of collecting several documents related to the problem that the writer will research from both primary and secondary legal materials. The legal materials that are relevant to the problem in this writing are then systematically obtained and analyzed using legal interpretation and argumentation methods. After obtaining the analysis results, they will be explained descriptively so that the expected results can explain the legal policy framework for developing tourist villages based on green tourism in Gianyar, Bali so that a comprehensive picture of the problems studied is obtained.

3. Discussion

A. Legal Policy Framework for the Development of Tourist Villages Based on Green Tourism in Gianyar, Bali

In recent years, there has been a change in tourism trends from mass tourism to tourism activities that are more friendly to nature and local communities. This change shows that tourists are no longer oriented towards conventional products offering recreational activities but have shifted to products emphasizing elements of experience, uniqueness, authenticity, and respect for the environment and local culture. This shift in tourist interest supports the growth and development of tourist villages managed by local communities and emphasizes rural conditions so that it can trigger an increase in the economic sector while maintaining the authenticity of the village environment and culture [10]. The development of tourist villages is considered capable of minimizing the potential for urbanization of communities from rural to urban areas because it can create economic activities in rural areas that are based on tourism activities or what is called a tourism economy [11].

Tourism contributes significantly to global economic growth, job creation, and infrastructure development. Notes on Economic Driving Events for Bali Province for Quarter IV-2023 show that the number of foreign and domestic tourist visits increased by 38.80 percent and 19.98 percent, respectively [12]. The rapid expansion and exploration of the tourism industry's development have had negative impacts on the environment and society, thereby encouraging the emergence of environmentally friendly tourism. Eco-friendly tourism emphasizes responsible travel practices that prioritize environmental conservation, social and cultural sensitivity, and economic sustainability [13].

Green tourism is an important component of sustainable tourism. Initially, green tourism was defined as one of the steps in tourism with indicators of sustainable development that is environmentally friendly and still pays attention to the social, economic, and cultural aspects of local communities. Green tourism functions to minimize negative impacts through efforts to conserve natural resources [14]. Green tourism is a narrowly defined approach to environmentally friendly tourism development, which takes environmentally friendly, scientific, low-carbon, and sustainable development as its development principle, uses environmentally friendly technological innovation to develop tourism resources scientifically and appropriately, focusing on connotation and quality tourism, and

changing the traditional approach to tourism development into a modern approach to tourism development with coordinated economic, social and environmental development [15].

The development of Green Tourism is very important to encourage tourist travel to help support natural and cultural aspects while encouraging respect and conservation of resources and cultural diversity. According to Dodds and Joppe, the concept of green tourism can be divided into four components, namely [16]:

1. Environmental responsibility, namely protecting, preserving, and improving the natural environment to ensure the long-term sustainability of the ecosystem.
2. Local economic vitality, namely supporting local community economic and business activities for the sake of local community economic sustainability.
3. Cultural diversity, namely respecting and appreciating the cultural diversity of the community to ensure their welfare as sustainable hosts
4. Achievement of experience, namely providing experience to enrich insight through active participation in harmony in maintaining involvement with people, nature, and culture.

The role of the green economy in developing tourist villages has significant implications for economic and environmental transformation at the local level. The green economy concept refers to a development approach that focuses on sustainability and is environmentally friendly. Its application in the context of tourist villages opens up various opportunities and challenges [17]. The development of rural green tourism encourages the improvement of rural areas, roads, and villages as a whole and stimulates social infrastructure development. The development of rural eco-tourism plays an important role in raising the cultural and educational level of the rural population [18]. A green economy in tourist villages can encourage local economic empowerment. Local communities can increase their income by utilizing the potential of local resources, such as organic agricultural products and traditional crafts. Thus, the development of tourist villages provides economic benefits for tourism entrepreneurs and directly empowers local communities [19].

The green tourism concept supports sustainable development by managing tourism and considering the needs of future generations. This approach aims to improve the quality of nature and the environment while ensuring the strengthening and sustainability of the local economy. Green tourism emphasizes inclusive tourism industry practices, especially on a small scale, by providing facilities owned by individuals or local communities. In contrast to the concept of mass tourism, which is generally applied, green tourism prioritizes inclusive activities and pays attention to local involvement. Green tourism activities focus more on nature-based activities or the "back to nature" concept. This approach seeks to create a more harmonious relationship between tourists and the surrounding environment and encourage understanding and appreciation of natural beauty. Overall, this concept is an attractive alternative to designing sustainable tourism management [20].

The government has a very important role in directing and

supporting the development of tourist villages, one of which is that the government is responsible for creating policies and regulations that support the development of tourist villages. This includes drafting clear regulations related to operational permits, environmental protection, cultural protection, and other aspects related to tourism. Clear policies provide direction for tourist village managers and industry players [21]. As a policy maker, the Government needs to encourage the community and related parties in the tourism sector to carry out activities towards green tourism in all aspects of their activities. The aim is to be able to compete with foreign countries that already have or are preparing to move towards green tourism to increase foreign exchange or regional income [22].

Forms of community tourism development can be carried out in 3 ways, namely: (1) self-help (entirely from the community); (2) Partnership (through large/small entrepreneurs or adoptive father system); and (3) assistance by Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) or universities as long as the community is deemed unable to be independent, but if they are deemed capable of being independent, they are slowly abandoned by the companion [23]. The rapid development of tourist villages needs to be supported by the preparation of guidelines for developing tourist villages which can then be used as a reference for all stakeholders in developing tourist villages which can provide benefits to local communities through the development of sustainable tourism through local community-based tourism. It is hoped that this guideline will encourage sustainable tourism development and more focused and planned management of tourist villages [24]. The legal policy for developing green tourism-based tourist villages is outlined in the form of statutory regulations.

The legal basis for tourism development in accordance with development principles is Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 10 of 2009 concerning Tourism in Article 6, which states that tourism development is carried out based on the principles as intended in Article 2, which are realized through the implementation of tourism development plans by taking into account diversity, uniqueness, and cultural and natural characteristics, as well as the human need to travel, Article 8 paragraph (1) which states: Tourism development is carried out based on a tourism development master plan consisting of a national tourism development master plan, a provincial tourism development master plan, and a regency/city tourism development master plan [25].

Article 11 states: The government and institutions related to tourism carry out tourism research and development to support tourism development. Furthermore, there is Article 12 paragraph (1), which states: Determination of strategic tourism areas is carried out by taking into account the following aspects [26]:

1. Natural and cultural tourism resources that have the potential to become tourism attractions;
2. Basic potential;
3. Strategic location that plays a role in maintaining national unity and territorial integrity;
4. Protection of certain locations that have a strategic role in maintaining the function and carrying capacity of

Table 2
Strategic targets and focus of tourist village development [29]

No.	Strategic Targets and Focus	The First Year	The Second Year	The Third Year	The Fourth Year	The Fifth Year
	Tourist Village Development	Research Assistance	Implementation Assistance	Implementation Assistance	Implementation Assistance	Evaluation
1	Research Policy and Infrastructure and Innovation in the Region	1. Identification 2. Determination	1. Implementation 2. Evaluation	1. Implementation 2. Evaluation	1. Implementation 2. Evaluation	1. Policy's Revision 2. Strengthening
2	Institutional and Supporting Capacity for Research and Innovation	1. Introduction 2. Understanding	1. Strengthening	1. Strengthening	1. Strengthening	1. Revision
3	Research and Innovation Partnership	1. Identification 2. Determination	1. Implementation 2. Evaluation	1. Implementation 2. Evaluation	1. Implementation 2. Evaluation	1. Policy's Revision 2. Strengthening
4	Research and Innovation Culture	1. Introduction 2. Understanding	1. Strengthening	1. Strengthening	1. Strengthening	1. Revision
5	Integration of Research and Innovation in the Regions	1. Identification 2. Learning	1. Implementation 2. Evaluation	1. Implementation 2. Evaluation	1. Implementation 2. Evaluation	1. Policy's Revision 2. Strengthening
6	Alignment with Global Developments	1. Introduction 2. Understanding	1. Alignment	1. Alignment	1. Alignment	1. Developing

the environment;

5. Strategic locations that have a role in efforts to preserve and utilize cultural assets;
6. Community readiness and support; and
7. Specificity of the region.

Regulation of the Minister of Tourism and Creative Economy/Head of the Tourism and Creative Economy Agency of the Republic of Indonesia Number 1 of 2023 concerning Technical Instructions for the Use of Special Non-Physical Allocation Funds for Tourism Services Funds determines that Regional Governments that have Tourism Villages must carry out Tourism Village Management Training. Tourist Village Management Training aims to increase the knowledge, motivation and competence of tourist village managers to be more professional and qualified in managing tourist villages and providing services to tourists. The target that must be achieved from this training is that participants know and understand basic tourism knowledge; participants know and understand the importance of *Sapta Pesona* in creating a Tourism Consciousness society; participants know and understand the institutional development of tourism village management; Participants know and understand the development and management of tourism products in tourist villages.

The development of tourist villages in Gianyar district is in accordance with the Vision of the Regional Government of Gianyar Regency, namely "The realization of a Gianyar community that is happy, prosperous, safe and peaceful, independent, with integrity, based on Tri Hita Karana, through the Universally Planned National Development Pattern". the direction of the Gianyar Regency's medium-term regional development policy for 2018-2023, one of which is Building inclusive and culture-based tourism. The direction of Gianyar Regency's tourism development, based on the Regional Tourism Development Master Plan, includes quality, community empowerment-based, sustainable tourism development. and integrated between sectors, regional tourism development that prioritizes the superiority of local wisdom in accordance with Balinese and National tourism development priorities, regional tourism development based on cultural,

natural/environmental attractions based on harmony between humans, nature/environment, culture and religion and regional tourism development oriented towards equitable regional economic growth, increasing employment opportunities, reducing poverty, preserving culture and nature/the environment.

Tourism products that tourists want to enjoy, such as natural and cultural tourist destinations, need to be supported by infrastructure and facilities such as hotels, restaurants, transportation, souvenirs, entertainment, and other supporting attractions that must be able to improve the quality of life of the tourist destination area itself. Humans carry out tourism activities to seek, enjoy, experience, and appreciate different, unique, and interesting cultures and nature. This is based on basic human needs (human rights) in their free time by improving the quality of life and degree of humanity (self-actualization, psychological, sociological, sense of security, physiological). If you look at Law Number 9 of 1990 concerning Tourism, it is no longer in accordance with tourism developments at the national and international levels. In reality, the policies made only regulate tourism businesses but sanctions are not implemented. This is because the basic concept/soul (paradigm) is not listed and not explained in the body of Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 10 of 2009 concerning Tourism [4].

The legal policy for developing tourist villages does not only involve the role of the government but also the community. Local communities are increasingly recognized for their role in promoting environmentally friendly tourism. Their active participation and commitment to sustainable practices is essential. Involving local communities in planning and management is critical to successful implementation. Fair distribution of benefits, economic incentives, and preservation of cultural heritage strengthen community involvement. Training and capacity-building initiatives empower communities to engage in sustainable tourism [27].

Table 3
Data on tourist villages in Gianyar Regency, Bali based on mayor/regent determination decree

No.	Tourism Village Data-Based Mayor/Regent Determination Decree		Category	Information
	Tourist Villages	District		
1	Singapadu Tengah	Sukawati	Advanced	Gianyar Regent Regulation, No429/E-02/2017 concerning Determination of Tourist Villages in Gianyar Regency
2	Singapadu Kaler	Sukawati	Developed	Gianyar Regent Regulation, No429/E-02/2017 concerning Determination of Tourist Villages in Gianyar Regency
3	Taro	Tegallalang	Advanced	Gianyar Regent Regulation, No429/E-02/2017 concerning Determination of Tourist Villages in Gianyar Regency
4	Kerta	Payangan	Developing	Gianyar Regent Regulation, No429/E-02/2017 concerning Determination of Tourist Villages in Gianyar Regency
5	Batubulan	Sukawati	Advanced	Gianyar Regent Regulation, No429/E-02/2017 concerning Determination of Tourist Villages in Gianyar Regency
6	Kemenuh	Sukawati	Advanced	Gianyar Regent Regulation, No429/E-02/2017 concerning Determination of Tourist Villages in Gianyar Regency
7	Mas	Ubud	Independent	Gianyar Regent Regulation, No429/E-02/2017 concerning Determination of Tourist Villages in Gianyar Regency
8	Kendran	Tegallalang	Developing	Gianyar Regent Regulation, No429/E-02/2017 concerning Determination of Tourist Villages in Gianyar Regency
9	Kedisan	Tegallalang	Pioneering	Gianyar Regent Regulation, No429/E-02/2017 concerning Determination of Tourist Villages in Gianyar Regency
10	Keramas	Blahbatuh	Developing	Gianyar Regent Regulation, No707/E-02/HK/2019 Concerning Tourist Villages in Gianyar Regency 2019
11	Pejeng Kangin	Tampak Siring	Developing	Gianyar Regent Regulation, No707/E-02/HK/2019 Concerning Tourist Villages in Gianyar Regency 2019
12	Petulu	Ubud	Developing	Gianyar Regent Regulation, No707/E-02/HK/2019 Concerning Tourist Villages in Gianyar Regency 2019
13	Tegallalang	Tegallalang	Advanced	Gianyar Regent Regulation, No707/E-02/HK/2019 Concerning Tourist Villages in Gianyar Regency 2019
14	Buahan Kaja	Payangan	Pioneering	Gianyar Regent Regulation, No707/E-02/HK/2019 Concerning Tourist Villages in Gianyar Regency 2019
15	Lebih	Gianyar	Pioneering	Gianyar Regent Regulation, No707/E-02/HK/2019 Concerning Tourist Villages in Gianyar Regency 2019
16	Sidan	Gianyar	Pioneering	Gianyar Regent Regulation, No707/E-02/HK/2019 Concerning Tourist Villages in Gianyar Regency 2019
17	Lodtunduh	Ubud	Pioneering	Gianyar Regent Regulation, No707/E-02/HK/2019 Concerning Tourist Villages in Gianyar Regency 2019
18	Singapadu	Sukawati	Pioneering	Gianyar Regent Regulation, No707/E-02/HK/2019 Concerning Tourist Villages in Gianyar Regency 2019
19	Celuk	Sukawati	Pioneering	Gianyar Regent Regulation, No707/E-02/HK/2019 Concerning Tourist Villages in Gianyar Regency 2019
20	Bedulu	Blahbatuh	Pioneering	Gianyar Regent Regulation, No 762/E.02/HK/2020 concerning Determination of Tourist Villages in Gianyar Regency
21	Manukaya	Tampak Siring	Pioneering	Gianyar Regent Regulation, No 762/E.02/HK/2020 concerning Determination of Tourist Villages in Gianyar Regency
22	Sayan	Ubud	Advanced	Gianyar Regent Regulation, No 762/E.02/HK/2020 concerning Determination of Tourist Villages in Gianyar Regency
23	Tampak Siring	Tampak Siring	Developing	Peraturan Bupati Gianyar, No 762/E.02/HK/2020 Tentang Penetapan Desa Wisata di Kabupaten Gianyar
24	Kelurahan Beng	Gianyar	Developing	Peraturan Bupati Gianyar, No 762/E.02/HK/2020 Tentang Penetapan Desa Wisata di Kabupaten Gianyar
25	Peliatan	Ubud	Advanced	Peraturan Bupati Gianyar No. 1311/E-02/HK/2021
26	Keliki	Tegallalang	Pioneering	Peraturan Bupati Gianyar No. 1311/E-02/HK/2021
27	Buruan	Blahbatuh	Pioneering	Peraturan Bupati Gianyar No. 18/E-02/HK/2021
28	Meliggih Kelod	Payangan	Advanced	Peraturan Bupati Gianyar No. 18/E-02/HK/2021
29	Pupuan	Blahbatuh	Pioneering	Peraturan Bupati Gianyar No. 18/E-02/HK/2021
30	Saba	Blahbatuh	Pioneering	Peraturan Bupati Gianyar No. 18/E-02/HK/2021
31	Sebatu	Tegallalang	Developing	Peraturan Bupati Gianyar No. 18/E-02/HK/2021
32	Batuan	Sukawati	Developing	Peraturan Bupati Gianyar No. 1311/E-02/HK/2021
33	Tampak Siring	Tampak Siring	Developing	Gianyar Regent Regulation, No 762/E.02/HK/2020 concerning Determination of Tourist Villages in Gianyar Regency
34	Kelurahan Beng	Gianyar	Developing	Gianyar Regent Regulation, No 762/E.02/HK/2020 concerning Determination of Tourist Villages in Gianyar Regency
35	Peliatan	Ubud	Advanced	Gianyar Regent Regulation No. 1311/E-02/HK/2021
36	Keliki	Tegallalang	Pioneering	Gianyar Regent Regulation No. 1311/E-02/HK/2021
37	Buruan	Blahbatuh	Pioneering	Gianyar Regent Regulation No. 18/E-02/HK/2021
38	Meliggih Kelod	Payangan	Advanced	Gianyar Regent Regulation No. 18/E-02/HK/2021
39	Pupuan	Blahbatuh	Pioneering	Gianyar Regent Regulation No. 18/E-02/HK/2021
40	Saba	Blahbatuh	Pioneering	Gianyar Regent Regulation No. 18/E-02/HK/2021
41	Sebatu	Tegallalang	Developing	Gianyar Regent Regulation No. 18/E-02/HK/2021
42	Batuan	Sukawati	Developing	Gianyar Regent Regulation No. 1311/E-02/HK/2021

B. Application of the Green Tourism Concept in the Development of Tourism Villages in Gianyar Regency

The formation of tourist villages in Gianyar Regency, Bali relies on the concept of green tourism. The concept of tourist villages is expected to provide variations in tourist attractions

so that they are not trapped in mass tourism because the villages where most of the tourist attractions are located certainly have local wisdom that has the potential to be developed and is certainly different from other villages. Through tourism villages, tourism will be created which can absorb rural labor (pro-job), grow the village economy (pro-growth) and as a tool

to reduce poverty rates (pro-poor) [28]. The targets, strategies and focus of tourism village development are reviewed in several indicators, namely policy and research and innovation infrastructure in the region, institutional capacity and supporting capacity for research and innovation, research and innovation partnerships, research and innovation culture, integration of research and innovation in the region and alignment with global development [29].

Determining a village to become a tourist village usually must meet several requirements, including 1) Having good accessibility, making it easier for tourists to visit using various types of transportation; 2) Must have interesting objects which can be in the form of nature, cultural arts, legends, local food, and so on to be developed as tourist attractions; 3) The community and village officials provide full support to the tourist village and tourists who visit their village; 4) Security in the village is guaranteed; 5) Adequate accommodation, telecommunications and labor are available; 6) Having a cool or cold climate; 7) Have relationships with other tourist attractions that are known to the wider community [30]. Gianyar Regency Government determines which villages will become tourist villages.

The development of tourist villages in Gianyar Regency is carried out continuously. Some of the tourist village developments that have been carried out include:

- a. Kerta Village was officially designated as one of the tourist villages in Gianyar Regency based on Regent's Decree Number 429/E-02/HK/2017. Kerta Village is one of nine villages in Payangan District, Gianyar Regency. Land conversion activities in this village are still very controlled. Based on the profile of Kerta Village in 2020, the productive agricultural land owned by Kerta Village reached 1,000.23 hectares, consisting of 224.88 hectares of rice fields, 628.81 hectares of dry land and 146.54 hectares of forest area. The people of Kerta Village really respect the customs and customs that come from ancestral heritage as well as people living in harmony with each other and taking great care of preserving the environment. This well-maintained environment makes Kerta Village very good for being developed as a natural tourism destination because the various natural potentials it has are still sustainable, such as forests, rivers, rice fields, and others. Likewise, with the cultural potential of the past and which is still alive today, including the sarcophagus site, the *Ulu Apad* government system, Bali Aga traditions and customs, caves, and others. These potentials are valuable capital in supporting tourism in Kerta Village [31].
- b. Sayan Village, as a village that has one mission, namely to make Sayan Village a tourist village, has several potentials, including three large potentials that are being developed and are also in planning. The first three potentials are natural *bija* tourism, water tubing tourism potential opportunities, and also the potential of Puri Sayan as a heritage tourism site for Sayan Village which the government and the local village community are currently planning. Apart from these three great

potentials, Sayan Village also has the potential for tirtan tourism for melukat. Melukat can be interpreted as cleansing oneself both physically and mentally, which is carried out by Hindus [32].

- c. Mas Village is one of the villages in the Central Bali region, precisely in Ubud District area, Gianyar Regency. Since the time of the kingdom in Bali, Mas Village has always had a strategic position in its history. Mas Village is a tourist route between Ubud, Sukawati and Tampaksiring which has produced many great figures and artists who produce extraordinary works in the fields of art, sculpture, masks, and paintings. The potential tourist attraction in Mas Village consists of expanses of rice fields that are starting to turn green with the traditional life of farmers becoming another side of life in a corner of Mas Village. Mas Village, which in its early days was an agricultural village, is still able to maintain its existence in the agricultural sector until now. Mas Village is a village that has many temples spread across the land in this village, more than 30 temples are spread out and have a very unique history and hold various historical heritage sites that are interesting to see. The development of tourism has made significant changes to the face of Mas Village. The village which was originally an agricultural village has now transformed into a village with modern acculturation where art shops are growing rapidly along with increasing tourist visits and the strategic position of Mas Village which is between Ubud, Tampaksiring and Sukawati tourist routes. The life of dance and percussion is an inseparable part of Mas Village, the existence of dance and percussion arts which are always present at every *yadnya* ceremony, makes these two types of art "steady" and long-lasting in their existence. As time goes by and the influence of tourism, the arts of dance and percussion are also starting to be commercialized with various innovations in regular performances or events that take place in Mas Village. Of course, typical Balinese culinary delights cannot be separated from the people of Mas Village, with the blend of Balinese spices (*Base Gede*) and mixed by experts, it will certainly provide a taste that is delicious and guaranteed to be addictive. Various art performances and various local, national, and even international events have been held in Mas Village, starting from local scale sculpture and mask exhibitions, the "Grebeg Aksara" red and white flag carnival, which involves many artists, stakeholders, and related officials in Bali to the Festival event. and Seminars "involving local, national, and international artists [8].

The development of rural tourism should fulfill the following planning principles: a) paying attention to the characteristics of the local environment, b) minimizing the negative impacts of tourism development in the village as little as possible, c) materials used that are appropriate to the local environment, d) operational materials that are environmentally friendly and can be used. recycled or/ recycled products and taking into

account the carrying capacity and capacity of the environment because rural tourism is not mass tourism, and e) involving village communities by making village communities actors in tourism activities, namely becoming direct/indirect owners of the tourist village and ownership of the land not redirected [33].

C. Feasibility Study of Building Arrangement and Environment of Ceking Rice Terrace Tourist Destination Area as a Tourist Village

The initiation of the arrangement of buildings and the regional environment in the tourist village in Ceking Rice Terrace area takes into account various legal policies. The legal umbrella for this tourism village development policy includes Law Number 26 of 2007 concerning Spatial Planning as amended several times, most recently with Law Number 6 of 2023 concerning the Determination of Government Regulations in Lieu of Law Number 2 of 2022 concerning Job Creation. Law, Bali Province Regional Regulation Number 2 of 2023 concerning Bali Province Regional Spatial Planning Plan for 2023-2043; Gianyar Regency Regional Regulation Number 2 of 2023 concerning Gianyar Regency Spatial Planning for 2023 – 2043 and Gianyar Regent Regulation, Bali Province, Gianyar Regent Regulation Number 1 of 2024. These provisions are the basis for the preparation of the Integrated Master Plan for the Development of the ULAPAN Tourism Area (Ubud, Tegallalang and Payangan) in Bali Province.

Tegallalang District is included in Zone 2, where the zone has the main function of tourism which emphasizes the potential for natural and cultural tourism by minimizing built space for environmental sustainability. Ceking Rice Terrace is one of the tourist destinations in Tegallalang Village, Tegallalang District, Gianyar, Bali, Indonesia.

Fig. 1. Tegallalang map

The development of a green tourism-based tourist village that is still being developed is Tegallalang tourist village with Ceking Rice Terrace tourist destination. One of the tourist attractions that offers beautiful natural views dominated by terraced rice fields is Ceking Rice Terrace, which is located in Gianyar district. Local and foreign tourists visit these tourist attractions, which have tourism potential. In the study regarding the Feasibility Study (FS) of Building Arrangement and Environment of Ceking Rice Terrace Tourist Destination Area, there is an analysis of potential in terms of building layout, environmental, social, economic and tourism planning as in the table 4.

Table 4
The potency of Ceking Rice terrace [34]

Potency	Description
Building layout	Ceking tourist area has a unique appearance of buildings that basically have Balinese architectural nuances. The unique appearance of this building can be developed as a distinctive characteristic or identity that can be built in Ceking area, especially for buildings related to tourism functions. The growth of buildings with various functions in the area can form a spatial pattern of the tourist area that is attractive in terms of appearance, dimensions, style, and architectural form as well as being a unique attraction.
Environmental governance	The regional environment is still dominated by green open space in the form of rice fields. However, there has been a change in land function from agriculture to trade and service functions, especially land located on the edge of the main road. Rice terraces have not been utilized optimally as a tourist attraction. This area also has river flows, good irrigation of rice fields, available road networks, clusters of buildings, and land availability.
Social	An authority institution for managing Ceking tourist area (BPOWC) has been formed, making coordinating and accounting for the area's management easier. The community through traditional institutions (customary/ <i>banjar</i>) in Tegallalang Village has been involved in managing Ceking tourist area, this is a form of support and commitment as well as empowerment of the local community. Agricultural and artistic activities (art, movement and sound) owned by the community can become components of cultural attractions that diversify the area's natural beauty.
Economy	The development of Ceking area into a tourist attraction with an average number of tourist visits of 900 people/day has sparked various economic activities, both trade and services related to tourism. Developing economic activity has provided opportunities for the development of various types of businesses and opened up job opportunities, so that the development of trade or service businesses in Ceking area will also contribute to the income of villages, traditional villages and regional governments.
Tourism	In terms of location, Ceking area is very strategic because it is located between Ubud and Kintamani tourist areas, so it can be an alternative destination to visit and can also be used as a stopover or rest area. Ceking area has several objects that have the opportunity to be developed as attractions, not only physical rice terraces but also agricultural activities for example, thereby diversifying tourist attractions. This area has relatively easy accessibility to reach the area and there are several facilities needed to support tourist activities. The regional tourism management authority institution, which in this case is Ceking Tourism Object Management Agency, is a regional tourism management authority institution which is the manager and person responsible for tourism activities in the area. This area has also met the needs for developing tourist attractions, namely attraction, amenities, accessibility and amenities.

Fig. 2. Ceking rice terrace

Based on 2023 tourism office data, the growth in tourist visits until May 2023 will average 11%, seen from ticket sales. The increase in tourist visits has had an impact on community businesses in Ceking tourist attraction. People's income after working in Ceking Rice Terrace area increased. The existence of Ceking Rice Terrace area has also resulted in increased employment opportunities, especially for the local community, as well as the arrangement of infrastructure around the tourist area for the convenience of visitors. The steps taken to develop tourism in Gianyar district, Bali are destination arrangement, institutional strengthening, industrial development, and marketing expansion. Based on data obtained from the Regional Development Planning and Development Research Agency of Gianyar Regency, regarding the arrangement of buildings and the environment of Ceking tourist destination area. Rice Terrace that several aspects are being highlighted by the local government in developing this tourist village, including technical aspects of environmental management regarding circulation systems and connecting routes, green management systems, infrastructure and utilities. Second, the technical aspects of building planning which include the basic shape and figure of the building mass, the location and orientation of the building, the height of the building and the architectural expression of the building. The three environmental aspects include land use structure, land use intensity, and environmental quality management. Fourth, social and economic aspects related to management institutions, business opportunities, and increasing income [34].

4. Conclusion

The development of green tourism is very important in encouraging tourist travel and supporting natural and cultural aspects. The government as a policy maker, needs to encourage the community and related parties in the tourism sector to carry out activities towards green tourism in all aspects of their activities. Gianyar Regency, Bali, Indonesia has 32 tourist villages designated based on the Mayor/Regent Determination Decree. The development of tourist villages in Gianyar Regency is being developed continuously, so the number will increase in the future. Since the end of 2023, Gianyar Regency Government has carried out a feasibility study on the building and environmental arrangement of Ceking Rice Terrace tourist destination to support the tourism village program. The steps taken to develop tourism in Gianyar district are destination planning, institutional strengthening, industrial development, and marketing expansion. However, in sustainable tourism development, the labeling of tourist villages must be followed by regular evaluation. Infrastructure development in the area

and towards the Tourism Village also needs to be considered.

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